

ANALYSIS OF RAILWAY SCALES DESIGNED FOR MEASURING ROLLING STOCK IN STATIC MODE.

Master's student: **Nurbayev Bobomurod Safar o'g'li**, MV-2 guruhi (TDTrU)

Master's student: **Abduvaliyev Javoxirxo'ja Alimxo'ja o'g'li** MV-2 guruhi (TDTrU)

Master's student: **Dexqonov Nurmuhammad Xasan o'g'li** MV-2 guruhi (TDTrU)

Anotation: Uniformity in terms of metrology and standardization and certification requirements has been agreed on the basis of Jaxon standards. But based on the laws of gravity and following the principles of universal gravitation, it is possible to understand that objects are heaviest at the poles of our planet and lightest at the equator. A brief analysis of this situation was made.

Key words: static scale, wagon scale, freight wagon, rolling stock, platform scale, "sleeper-sensor" scale, "rail-sensor" scale, weight, km/h, km.

The current method of weighing rolling stock on static scales is outdated and has long ceased to meet the requirements of modern production management systems. In order to statically weigh rolling stock on a wagon scale, it is necessary to separate the rolling stock and connect the loaded wagons to the wagon scales one after the other, and weigh them while they are stopped on the scale. Due to such stoppages, the cargo owners suffer losses amounting to millions of soums.

Increasing the production of raw materials and goods, taking into account the sharp increase in freight traffic associated with the development of railways, the problem of accounting and registration of goods has become urgent. In recent years, the development of the industry has set a number of new tasks related to the creation of automated systems of inventory and production management.

The history of wagon scales is more than 100 years old. Since the wagons move along the rails, designers and engineers have developed several different and very interesting technical solutions of wagon scales to weigh them.

Scales are easy to install, do not require the production of a cast concrete foundation, which reduces the time and cost of installing the equipment. Strain gauge sensors are used as measuring elements of the scales, which ensure high measurement accuracy and reliability of the scales even in unfavorable working conditions.

No other type of balance sheet has such a wide variety of operating principles. These are mechanical (handle) and electronic, hydraulic, pneumatic and electromechanical (hybrid), tensometric and optical wagon scales. However, the following three main types of strain gauges are most commonly used, namely:

- platform scales or bridge tensometric railway scales are direct "successors" of mechanical lever scales. The construction of the scales, roughly speaking, a platform for accepting the load - a "bridge" - is installed on top of the tensometric sensor.

To ensure accuracy over a wide temperature range, such railway scales use sensors with spherical surfaces that provide "self-centering" of the load receiving platform. On platform (bridge) wagon scales, wagons can be weighed statically, wagons moving at a speed of 15 km/h or in the mode of universal wagon scales, that is, both static and dynamic weighing;

- "sleeper-sensor" scales. The first design developments of such scales appeared in the 60s of the 20th century, but they were widely used at the beginning of the 21st century, so such scales are a relatively new design solution.

"Sleep-sensor" scales are a weighing device without a load receiving platform. The supports are mounted on special scale rails. Such scales are designed for weighing when moving at a speed of 60 km / h, but this design is also successfully used for weighing wagons in static mode;

- "rail-sensor" scales are made of two load sensors of railway rails. These scales were designed by Jack Cadicott of Weightronix and installed in the copper mines of Chile.

Basically, "rail-sensor" scales are designed for weighing at a speed of 60 km

per hour. The use of such scales for static weighing is very problematic, because the rails of the "scale section" are very short, and it is difficult to install the wheels of the wagons on them, especially since the wheelbase and number of axles are different in different models of wagons, possible.

In conclusion: As we can see, "Uzbekistan Railways" JSC, which is making a great contribution to the economy of our country, is making great changes and successes.

Above, we briefly got acquainted with the history and types of wagon scales that have been used in the railway system and are still being used.

Based on the above, we can see the great importance of wagon scales in the railway system, that is, in accounting for the goods transported by railway, in the correct organization of movement, in the correct operation of the rolling stock and commercial is of great importance in accounting.

References

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